

LONGITUDINAL CHANGES IN THE IRON PROFILES OF HIV PARTICIPANTS BEFORE AND DURING TREATMENT AT NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL NNEWI

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Abstract

HIV infection is associated with significant iron alterations ranging from iron deficiency to iron overload with faster disease progression, immune dysfunction and higher mortality. This study was conducted to provide information on the iron profile of patients with HIV on antiretroviral therapy (ART) and those not on ART. Blood samples were collected from 160 subjects. 80 HIV-seropositive individuals were tested at baseline, 4 months, and 8 months, 80 apparently healthy individuals with HIV seronegative as control. The total iron, total iron binding capacity, transferrin, and ferritin levels of the subjects were determined using standard methods after obtaining ethics approval and informed consent from the subjects. ANOVA, t-test, and Bonfereri post hoc test were used for statistical analysis. There were significant positive correlations between transferrin and total iron and between ferritin and total iron binding capacity ($r = 0.569$, $p = 0.022$; $r = 0.671$, $p = 0.004$). The findings showed that iron profiles played significant roles in the understanding and management of anemia in patients with HIV infection. This study underscored the importance of early HIV screening, timely treatment and continuous monitoring, especially in a resource-limited setting.

INTRODUCTION

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection and its sequelae, the acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS), are major causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide, accounting for over 35 million deaths since the first reported cases in 1983 (1). An estimated 36.7 million people are infected with HIV worldwide, and 69.5%

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of these people live in sub-Saharan Africa. In Nigeria, approximately 3.1% of the population is said to be infected with HIV (1). AIDS is characterized by various immune function abnormalities that manifest as opportunistic diseases that eventually lead to increased morbidity and mortality in affected individuals (2).

Iron is a trace element required for essential physiological and cellular pathways in all life forms, including oxygen transport to tissues via hemoglobin, oxidative energy production, cell proliferation, and immune function (3). Iron is required for pathogen growth and is a key micronutrient in the context of immune function, with a bidirectional association between iron status and infection. Iron deficiency has been associated with impaired immune function, bactericidal macrophage activity, and T-cell function (4). However, because pathogens also require iron for survival, iron sequestration by the host, is a defense mechanism and part of the innate immune response, and it has been associated with a lower incidence of bacterial and viral infections.

Findings from these studies have led to the use of iron deprivation to target some infections, such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (5).

Iron deficiency and anemia are common among HIV-infected individuals, and both low and high iron stores are associated with an increased risk of HIV disease progression and other adverse HIV-associated outcomes. Iron supplementation is the standard of care for anemia and anemia. However, several factors complicate the use of iron supplementation in individuals with HIV infection. Cell-based studies have found that iron promotes the growth and replication of HIV (6).

Iron deficiency anemia is the most prevalent nutritional deficiency, affecting several countries worldwide, with serious consequences for human health, social development, and the economy (7). Its etiology is diverse and can be attributed to nutritional deficiencies of iron, folic acid, vitamin A, C, or B₁₂, as well as numerous diseases, such as malaria, intestinal parasites, and hemoglobinopathy. Iron deficiency has been identified as the main factor contributing to anemia, so the terms “anemia” and “iron deficiency” are often treated as synonyms. As anemia is the most severe stage of iron deficiency, approximately 2.5 times more individuals are iron deficient than anemic (8). Studies have shown that anemia persists at high levels during infancy and childhood (9).

The potential for the body iron concentration to be raised in HIV infection due to their accumulation in tissues such as liver, heart, pancreas and cells like macrophages is enormous and may result in free radical generation and accelerated catabolism of ascorbic acid (10)

Experimental evidence has shown that serum iron may be increased or decreased depending on the stage of the disease. Although iron stores may decline in early asymptomatic HIV infection probably because of impaired absorption, they may increase with disease progression as iron in the macrophages and other cells (11).

Materials and Methods

Study design

The study was conducted at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH) Nnewi, Anambra State, Nigeria. This was a longitudinal study designed to evaluate the mechanism of anemia in HIV-seropositive individuals and those undergoing antiretroviral therapy at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi. The design consisted of two groups: HIV-positive individuals and HIV-seronegative individuals (control group). The individuals were recruited within Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital and were age-matched across these two groups with an age range of 20-55 years. The inclusion criteria included newly diagnosed HIV seropositive participants (Naïve) aged 20-55 who attend HIV clinic NAUTH and apparently healthy HIV seronegative participants also aged 20-55 who served as controls. The exclusion criteria included participants on antiretroviral therapy and those aged 20 and > 55years.

Ethical clearance and informed consent

The study design was approved by the Ethics Committee of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Anambra state, Nigeria, according to the principles expressed in the Declaration of Helsinki. The participants were informed about the study design, and only those who gave their consent were recruited for the study. The informed form was written and approved along with the ethical clearance obtained from the Ethics Committee of NAUTH Nnewi. Reference: NAUTH / CS/66/VOL.14/VER 3/33/2021/028.

The consent form was issued with the questionnaire during recruitment, which only those who agreed and volunteered to participate signed before their blood samples were collected. All the recruited participants were assured that the information obtained from them would be treated with uttermost confidentiality and they had the full right not to participate in or withdraw from the study at any point they deemed necessary.

2.3 Sample collection and analysis

The serum sample used for the study Two millimeters (2ml) of whole blood was aseptically drawn by venipuncture from each participant. Blood (2ml) was aseptically dispensed into plain sample tubes. The mixture was allowed to clot and spun for 10 min. Serum was separated into a new plain using a micropipette and stored. The samples were kept frozen at a temperature of -18°C until the biochemical analysis of the iron profiles was carried out.

Determination of human ferritin

Human ferritin level was determined using the ELISA method

Assay Procedure

The reagents were allowed to stand at room temperature {20 -25 °C, and microplates were arranged according to the number of samples. The desired number of coated strips was placed in the holder. 25µl of ferritin standards, controls, and samples were added into the wells.

100µl of Biotin reagent was added to each well. The plate was shaken for 10-30sec

The plate was covered and incubated at room temperature (20-25°C) for 30 min.

The liquid was decanted from all wells and washed three times with 300µl of washed buffer. Blotting was performed on absorbance paper and 100µl of enzyme reagent was added into each well. The plate was covered and incubated at room temperature (20-25°C for 30 min. 100µl of Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate was added to all wells.

Incubated for 15at room temperature and 50µl of stop solution was added to all wells.

The plate was shaken for 20-30 seconds for the complete mixture of the solution. The absorbance was read on the ELISA reader at 450nm within 15 min after the addition of stop solution.

Determination of human transferrin

The human transferrin level was determined by ELISA

Assay Procedure

The samples were brought to room temperature, and the microwave plate was arranged according to the number of samples. 100ul of test, standard, and blank samples were displaced on the eact well duplicate and assayed. The plate was covered, sealed, and incubated for 90 minutes at 37°C. The liquid was decanted from each well. 100µl of Biotinylated detection AB working solution (100 L) was added to each well, and the plate was covered, sealed, and incubated for 1 hour at 37°C. The solution from each was decanted and 3 50µl of wash buffer was added to each well. The wells were soaked for 1 min and dried against clean absorbent paper. This process was performed thrice. A microplate washer was used for all the steps and washes. The test strips were used after each wash, and the wells were not dried.

100µl of Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) conjugate working solution was added to each well.

The plate was covered, sealed, and incubated at 37°C for 30 min. The solution was decanted well and washed five times. 90µl of substrate reagent was added to each well. The plate was covered, sealed and incubated at 37°C for 15 min. The plate was placed away from light, and the reaction time reduced with the development of the actual color change, which was below 30min. The microplate reader was preheated for 15 min before measurement. 50µl of stop solution was added to each well, and the optical density of each well was read at once using a microplate reader read at 450nm.

Serum iron and total iron binding capacity

Serum iron and total iron binding capacity were estimated using the colorimetric method

Assay procedure

The sample and reagents were brought to room temperature and arranged according to the number of samples. 500µl of sample were added in the respective tubes. 50µl iron-free water was added to the blank. The instrument was zeroed at 560nm with a blank. The absorbance of all tubes was read and recorded (A1 reading).

50µl iron color reagent was added to the tubes and mixed. All the tubes were placed in heating bath for 10 minutes at 37°C. The instrument was zeroed at 560nm using a blank reagent. The absorbance of all tubes was read and recorded (A2 reading).

Calculations

A = absorbance

STD = standard

(A2 Test –A1 Test)

----- × Conc. of Std)

(A2 Std A1 Std)

UIBC (unsaturated iron –binding capacity)

The tubes were labeled blank, standard, control, and test. 2.0ml of unsaturated iron binding capacity buffer reagent was added into the respective tubes, while 1.0ml of iron-free water was added to the blank tube and mixed. 0.5ml of the iron standard solution plus 0.5ml of iron free water were added to the standard tube. 0.5ml of the sample and 0.5ml of the iron standard were added to the tube labeled test. The spectrophotometer was zeroed with the blank and read at 560nm. The absorbance of all tubes read and recorded (A1 reading).

0.05ml of iron color reagent was added to all tubes. The solution was mixed and place the water bath at 37°C for 10min. The spectrophotometer was zeroed using a blank at 560nm wavelength. The absorbance of all the tubes read (A2 reading) and recorded.

UIBC Calculation

Conc of Std - A2test –A1test x Conc of Std

A2 = A1 Std

= UIBC (µg/dl)

Statistical Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 was used for statistical analysis. The data obtained were presented in tables, Student's t-test was used to compare differences between means, and analysis of variance with Bonferroni post hoc test was used to compare more than two independent variables. The level of significance was set at p<0.05).

RESULTS

No significant difference was found in the mean level of total iron among various therapy durations. Baseline 42.29±4.69, 4th month 42.75±6.47 and 8th 37.75±1.49 (p >0.05) . It also showed significantly higher mean

level of transferrin (baseline 214.13±31.27, 8th month 134.44±31.60) ferritin (baseline 392.64±163.78 , 8th month 210.81±87.08) and total iron binding capacity in baseline (470.81±108.39) when compared to 8month (p < 0.05) and 4th month when compared to 8th month transferrin 4th month 195.56±45.91, ferritin 4th month 342.50±150.24 and tbc 4th month 467.56±90.99 (p < 0.05). However, they did not differ significantly at baseline compared with at 4 months (p < 0.05). (Table 1).

The mean baseline levels of transferrin, ferritin and total iron binding capacity (185.63±64.54, 282.95±180.06, 350.91±182.32) were significantly high compared to control(136.11±45.15, 98.86±229.68, 246.85±113.09)(p ≤0.05) respectively, however the mean level of total iron did not differ significantly in baseline(39.42±17.19) compared to control(36.86±11.76) (p≥0.05). (Table 2).

There was significant positive correlation between transferrin and total iron (r = 0.569 p 0.022) and ferritin (r= 0.671p 0.004) at 8thmonth (p < 0.05). In addition there was a significant positive correlation between total iron and total iron binding capacity (r= 0.664 p 0.005) at 8th month (p < 0.05). (Table 3).

Table 1. Levels of total iron, transferrin and ferritin in HIV-infected individuals at baseline, 4th month and 8th month of treatment

Samples	Total iron (µmol/l)	Transferrin (ug/dl)	Ferritin (ng/ml)	Tbc (µmol/l)
Baseline (A) (n=80)	43.29±4.69	214.13±31.27	392.64±163.78	470.81±108.39
4th month (B) (n=80)	42.75±4.67	195.56±45.91	342.50±150.24	467.56±90.99
8th month (C) (n=80)	37.75±1.49	134.44±31.60	210.81±87.08	318.75±80.24
F-value	0.926	27.439	11.303	12.664
P-value	0.352	0.001*	0.001*	0.001*
A vs B	0.909	0.184	0.17	1.000
A vs C	1.000	0.001*	0.003*	0.001*
B vs C	0.986	0.001*	0.031*	0.002*

Statistical significance at p <0.05

TIBC total iron binding capacity

Table 2 Comparison between the iron profiles of HIV-infected individuals at baseline treatment and the control group.

Parameters	Baseline n= 80)	Control group (n = 80)	t-values	p-values
Total Iron	43.29±4.69	40.71±11.76	1.064	0.145.
Transferrin	214.13±31.27	136.11 ± 45.15	5.445	0.001*
Ferritin	392.64±163.78	98.86 ± 229.68	5.463	0.001*
TIBC	470.81±108.39	246.85 ± 113.09	4.200	0.001*

Statistically Significance at P < 0.05

TIBC total iron binding capacity

Table 3. Correlation of levels of iron profiles in the baseline, 4th month and 8th month samples

Correlation	Baseline		4 th month		8 th month	
	R-value	P-value	R-value	P-value	R-value	P-value
Total iron vs. Transferrin	0.110	0.684	0.535	0.033*	0.569	0.022*
Total iron vs Ferritin	0.177	0.512	0.238	0.376	0.469	0.067
Total iron vs. TIBC	-0.390	0.136	0.549	0.028	0.664	0.005*
Transferrin vs. Ferritin	0.280	0.439	0.423	0.102	0.671	0.004*
Transferrin vs. TIBC	0.553	0.026*	0.767	0.001*	0.478	0.061
Ferritin vs. TIBC	-0.080	0.769	0.369	0.159	0.737	0.001*

*P is significant at alpha level <0.05

TIBC Total iron binding capacity

DISCUSSION

The global burden of HIV infection is substantial and anemia is one of the most common indicator of the severity of HIV, often predicting mortality and disease progression among people living with HIV (PLWHIV).

In this study, the mean levels of total iron binding capacity, ferritin, and transferrin were significantly decreased at the fourth and eighth months of HAART treatment compared with baseline. They decreased were dependent on treatment duration the decrease was a sign of therapeutic response to antiretroviral therapy. The mean levels of total iron binding capacity. Ferritin, and transferrin were significantly increased in participants compared with the control group, which may be due to disease severity. This work concurred with the work of a previous work (12), which reported an increased in serum transferrin and total iron binding capacity during iron deficiency anemia to boost iron transport but decreases with inflammation.

It was also in tandem with the work of (13), who reported that high serum ferritin levels are common in children with HIV and are related to the immunological progression of the disease. Following the initiation of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART), at the fourth and eighth months of therapy, significant reductions in serum ferritin, transferrin,

Total iron binding capacity levels were observed, indicating reduced activity and improved disease

In this study, the mean levels of total iron were not statistically significant among the groups (baseline to 8 months), which may be due to ethnic diversity. This did not concur with the work of (14) who reported that higher serum iron is associated with increased oxidant stress in men with HIV infection.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that HIV infection is associated with significant alterations in iron metabolism, with anemia remaining a prominent complication among people living with HIV (PLWHIV). At baseline, HIV-seropositive participants exhibited elevated inflammatory and iron-related parameters compared with apparently healthy controls.

Reflecting disease severity and impaired erythropoiesis.

This study confirms that antiretroviral therapy plays a significant role in HIV-associated derangement and burden reduction, thereby improving the health status of affected individuals.

Recommendations

Routine assessment of iron profile should be incorporated into the standard clinical management of people living with HIV.

Early diagnosis and prompt initiation of antiretroviral therapy should be encouraged to prevent or reduce the incidence of HIV-associated anemia and its complications. Individuals with HIV infection with persistent anemia should undergo further evaluation for iron dysregulation

Further longitudinal studies involving larger populations are recommended to explore ethnic and regional variations in iron metabolism among individuals with HIV infection.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical clearance to conduct this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital.

Competing Interests

The authors declared that no competing interest exists.

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